

**THE INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION ON INTERNET SPACE AS A MEANS
OF DEVELOPING MULTICULTURAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN RUSSIA
AND KAZAKHSTAN**

Raisa Arkadyevna Arzumanova

PhD, candidate of pedagogical sciences
Associate professor
Peoples Friendship University of Russia
Associate professor
arzumanowa@mail.ru

Galina Kaskarbekovna Bokizhanova

PhD, candidate of pedagogical sciences
Associate professor
Academy "Bolashaq" Karaganda, Republic of Kazakhstan
(ORCID 0000-0003-2589-527X)
galiyakaz68@gmail.com

Nurgul Baltabayevna Seisekeyeva

Doctoral student in pedagogical sciences, doctoral school of «Cognition, language,
education»
of Aix-Marseille University
ADEF laboratory (France)
n.seisekeyeva@sorbonne.kz

Bayan Mukushevna Ibraeva

PhD, candidate of philological sciences, professor
Academy "Bolashaq", Karaganda, Republic of Kazakhstan
(ORCID 0000-0002-5964-2492)
ibraeva56@mail.ru

Abstract. The article is devoted to the consideration of the problem of intercultural communication in the Internet space. This problem is determined by active integration processes taking place in Russia and Kazakhstan, within the framework of the transition from bipolar to polypolar cooperation, from dialogue to polylogue of cultures. All this determines *the relevance* of the research topic. *The subject* of the research is the features of the Internet space as a method of intercultural communication and a means of forming multicultural competence in the Russian and Kazakh student environment. *The purpose* of the study is to identify and study the features of the formation of multicultural competence among students of Russia and Kazakhstan through communication in the Internet space. Among the main research *methods*: 1) theoretical methods (interdisciplinary & functional analysis, synthesis); 2) empirical methods (observation, diagnostic methods, experimental work, system and theoretical analysis, the method of expert assessments, interviewing, quantitative methods of processing results); 3) statistical methods (statistical processing of results). Based on the analysis, the author notes that recently the Internet space has become an important channel of communication and information for the majority of Russian and Kazakh students. This provides the possibility of two-way active communication with almost the whole world. Communication with foreign citizens allows you to learn about the culture of different peoples, adopt foreign words and expressions and introduce them into your own language and culture.

Key words: intercultural communication; internet space; Russian and Kazakh students; multicultural competence; common communication environment.

I. Introduction

Interest in the study of intercultural communication in the Internet space as a means of creating multicultural competence was formed under the influence of global processes. Today in the world, intercultural ties, international communication are becoming constant and fairly frequent. This is facilitated by an increase in the number of transnational firms, intensive development of the tourism sector, an increase in migration processes, an increase in the number of international marriages, the adoption of foreign children, etc. [15].

Integration globalizations in Russia and Kazakhstan, the gradual transformation of bipolar cooperation into polypolar ties of cultures, the progressive information activity of the younger generation, the establishment of intercultural ties and the implementation of intercultural communication should be based on tolerant, non-hostile, pacifist beliefs.

As in reality, in the Internet space, the dialogue of cultures is a property of social life, in which multicultural competence is formed through cultural cooperation in the space-time dimension [2]. The student environment of Russia and Kazakhstan, as a world youth community as a whole, is a special social and cultural phenomenon, a kind of subculture that has importance, significance, information sources and communication channels. Sometimes communication channels go beyond the limits of interpersonal communication, and contacts are established between cultures - both with representatives of a similar subculture in their own country and abroad [6; 13].

Thus, the Internet space has become the main information source and means of communication for a huge number of Russian and Kazakh students, giving a chance for mutual, multicultural communication with almost the entire globe. Through the global network, student representatives take part in a new, modern form of communication, i.e. in the information polylogue of cultures, unfolding in the space of virtual reality and characterized by peculiar means of verbal / non-verbalism. This allows intercultural contacts to rely not only on their own experience, but also on everything that is contained in the phenomenon of virtual reality. All of the above determined the relevance of the topic of this research.

The *subject* of this research is the features of the Internet space as a method of intercultural communication and a means of forming multicultural competence in the Russian and Kazakh student environment. The purpose of the study is to study the features of the formation of multicultural competence among students of Russia and Kazakhstan through communication in the Internet space. The novelty of the research lies in the fact that for the first time the Internet space is considered as a special way of intercultural interaction and the formation of multicultural competence in the youth, student environment.

What is the impact of the global network on culture - this issue is not fully understood at the present time. However, a large number of both positive and negative actions of the Internet have been noticed in relation to the formation of multicultural competence [1; eighteen]. First of all, this affects the processes of deformation of the language. We believe that a painstaking study of the impact of the Internet space on the level of formation of multicultural competence will help the development and improvement of the dialogue and polylogue of cultures in the space of virtual reality.

II. Research methods

The theoretical and methodological basis of this research includes: functional and systemic principles of the research; principles of the theory of intercultural communication. In addition, the theoretical basis of this work consists of conceptual provisions and works developed in the context of such sciences as philology, cultural studies, sociology, considering, incl. the theory of intercultural communication, the nature of the information environment, the phenomenon of information culture. Research methods cover a complex of traditional, standard methods and the latest information analysis tools, namely:

1. *Theoretical:*

- functional and interdisciplinary analysis and synthesis in the study and generalization of scientific works, including dissertations on issues similar to those considered in this study;

2. *Empirical:*

- observation;
- diagnostic methods (survey using various types of questionnaires, testing, monitoring, conversation, etc.);
- experimental and experimental work to study the possibilities of the Internet space in intercultural contact;
- theoretical and system analysis;
- method of interviewing;
- method of expert assessments;
- method of quantitative data processing.

3. *Statistical:*

- statistical processing of research results.

The social networks “Vkontakte”, “Facebook”, “Instagram”, “Twitter” which are popular among students, were chosen as an experimental base for the study.

III. Research results

In order to identify and study the main characteristics of intercultural communication in the space of the global Internet, in the course of our study, a survey was conducted of representatives of the student community in the amount of 400 people, including students from different cities of Russia and Kazakhstan.

The purpose of the survey was to determine the significance and main directions of the development of intercultural Internet communication. According to the research, the absolute majority of the surveyed students - 100% - use social networks and the Internet, which indicates their unconditional popularity in the modern world. Among them, 67% communicate with foreigners on the Internet, and each of the respondents notes the positive impact of such communication.

In addition, the results of the survey show that the social network "Vkontakte" is considered the most demanded and popular for communication with foreigners, as 51% of respondents believe. The second most popular social network in the student community is the social network "Facebook", with the help of which 27% of respondents communicate with foreigners. In third place is Instagram. According to the data obtained, 72% of students are subscribed to the accounts of foreign celebrities on this social network. It is with the help of “Instagram” that young people follow the life of world “stars”. Twitter is in fourth position.

One of the suggested questions in the questionnaire was the following: "What words / expressions have you adopted from foreign interlocutors via the Internet?" We received the answers hugs, okey, current mood, lol, drama, hi, etc. In the process of dialogue with representatives of other cultures, the respondents learn the characteristic features of the national mentality, traditions and customs of foreign countries, news of politics, economics, weather, ways of manifesting individuality, features of everyday life. 96% of students note that knowledge of foreign languages is improving through intercultural Internet communication.

Note that the lexical aspect of intercultural communication is of particular interest. Therefore, having studied the verbal means of Internet communication of students in Russia and Kazakhstan, we can say that from the point of view of vocabulary, the specificity of Internet communication comes down to word formation. In addition, there are cases of occasional use of tokens (a word previously used in standard communication in Internet communication begins to function differently). Let's consider an example of communication from the “WeChat” application:

Example № 1

«Hello, everybody. Friend of mine is looking for a guy and girl for real estate advertisement shooting. This Thursday 10 in the morning just for 3-4 hours. Salary is negotiable. If you are interested, please text me».

In this example, the use of the token text is of interest. Previously, it was used only as a noun, but in this case the word is used as a verb form, which means 'contact by sending a message'. Popularity in intercultural Internet communication among Russian and Kazakh students has gained the expression what's up, which has spread widely first in the United States and then around the world and has become a fashionable form of greeting.

It is estimated that 81% of the students surveyed use it in their speech. Expression options are wassup, wazzup, sup. Another popular lexeme through which emotions are expressed in the process of Internet communication is lol (abbreviation of the English phrase lot of laugh) [9, p. 128]. According to the survey data, this lexeme is used by about 73% of the respondents.

Russian and Kazakh students participating in Internet communication expand the vocabulary of Internet communication through the use of lexical borrowings. Since the original language of the global network was English, most of the words for Internet slang are borrowed from it [5]. The server, no, the site, etc. are barbarisms that have penetrated the Russian language through Internet communication.

In linguistic science, a similar phenomenon is called runglish. It should be noted that communication in the Internet space is characterized by the presence of onomastic vocabulary, since users - communicants - assign themselves names that can be real (according to our survey, they are used by about 30% of students), and nicknames - fictitious pseudonyms (they are used by the overwhelming most of the respondents - 70%). The use of English borrowings through transliteration is another feature of verbal intercultural communication on the Internet, observed in 62% of the students who took part in the survey.

Example No. 2

"You're talking about business communication, and I'm talking about blah blah with friends. All this I mean is that we are actually halfway to communication with binds and hotkeys."

As can be seen from the example, the communicant uses several specific lexical units related to verbal linguistic means characteristic of communication in the Internet space: blah-blah, friends, binds, hotkeys. Among the listed lexemes, the first two refer to borrowings from the English language used in modern colloquial speech, the other two refer to special words from computer discourse. The lexeme blah-blah in the Russian language of Internet communication came from English, where blah-blah means 'chatter'. This lexical unit is not new, it was used in literary works of the Perestroika period. For example, S. Sokolov in his work "Palisandria" writes: "Imagine what a publicity!" - shared his thoughts with Andropov. - "The mass media will positively cut short. they say, blah-blah-blah, boo-boo-boo. The most indecent flight of the century" [4, 35].

According to the definition given by the Dictionary of the Russian Argo, a friend (or friend, friend) is 'friend, friend, girlfriend, girlfriend'. This lexeme was borrowed from English and comes from friend, used in a similar meaning [3, 578]. The lexeme bind is also of English origin, but its use is associated only with computer discourse. The lexical unit comes from the English bind, which means 'to bind', 'to bind'. A bind is a method of binding specific actions to keys or shortcuts on the keyboard or mouse. For the most part, binds are used in computer games.

Hotkey - borrowing from computer discourse in English; denotes the expression 'hotkeys'. This token is a key combination used to speed up the execution of certain actions in the operating system environment in general and software in particular. Hotkey corresponds to the Russian-language version of "keyboard shortcuts". The use of Anglicism is due to the author's desire to give his speech expression, as well as to save time, since the lexeme "hotkey" is shorter than "keyboard shortcuts" or "hot keys".

Example No. 3

"Flood again. Live in the present, everything else comes from idleness. "

In this example, a foreign language borrowing flood is used. Flood - from the English 'flow'. Such a lexeme participates in the nomination of any discussion on the forum, etc., in no way relevant to the topic of discussion, turning the discussion into chaos.

Example No. 4

"The address is cut for some reason. I'll try this. Copy this link address and paste it as such into the address window. "

In this example of Internet communication, the word link borrowed from the English language is also used (from the English 'link'). Based on the above means of verbal Internet communication, it can be established that many lexemes are of foreign origin, borrowed into the language of communication through English, which again indicates its interethnic nature.

Two of the analyzed lexemes are units used in a conversational style of communication, two are units that function in computer slang. According to the research results, among the most popular borrowings in the context of verbal intercultural Internet communication are the lexemes trolling (48%) and cutie (41%). These borrowings are quickly mastered by the Russian language, obey the rules of Russian grammar, and acquire the corresponding characteristics of word formation.

Another way of word formation is "distortion of the existing orthoepic and spelling norms, which is called the "Albany language "; in it, the use of erratics, words with deliberate distortion of sound or spelling, gives the statement a special shade "[10, p. 133]. Quite often, new lexemes in Internet communication are formed by abbreviations, which, undoubtedly, is explained by the desire of the communicators to speed up the typing and sending of text during a conversation, bringing the typing speed closer to the speed of oral speech.

Most of the abbreviations used in Russian-language Internet communications are accepted in English and are often a transliteration of the original abbreviation. According to the survey, the most popular abbreviations used in Internet communication among students in Russia and Kazakhstan are IMHO and LOL (43% and 58%, respectively). The lexeme IMHO comes from the English abbreviation of the phrase in my humble opinion, meaning 'in my humble opinion'. In the language of Internet communication, this word is used to indicate the position of the author and functions as an introductory word.

Lexeme "lol" - from the English abbreviation of the expression laughing out loud with the meaning of 'violent laughter'. The respondents' answers also indicate the popularity of the abbreviation of Russian word combinations. Thus, 34% of the surveyed students noted the abbreviation PPCS, formed from the first letters of the phrase "I subscribe to every word." The use of abbreviations in the speech of students of Internet communication is quite reasonable, since communication in the global network as a whole refers to written forms of communication.

Thus, the lexical aspect of the dialogue of cultures in the Internet space consists in the peculiarities of word formation of linguistic units and also in the specificity of computer discourse. The vocabulary of the onomastic group plays an important role, since participants in Internet communication assign themselves "nicknames" - real or fictitious names.

In the language of Internet communication, borrowings from English prevail, incl. English abbreviations. In our opinion, in the modern world in connection with the development of the Internet and the transition of communication to virtual reality, the study of verbal means of Internet communication is becoming an integral part of the formation of multicultural competence.

Note also that according to our research, the overwhelming majority (98%) of the Russian and Kazakh students surveyed find out international news only through the Internet. The

overwhelming majority of respondents are interested in cultural and political news (78% and 66%, respectively), 36% prefer economic news.

A significant part of the students surveyed admits that intercultural communication is of great importance for effective communication and mutual understanding in the modern world. From their point of view, communication between cultures contributes to the successful development of processes of globalization and integration, the exchange of experience among citizens of different countries.

The Internet dialogue of cultures helps to foster tolerance towards representatives of other nationalities and races, and also helps to increase the level of knowledge of foreign languages and broaden horizons. 90% of respondents note that the possibilities of the global network space help to form the foundations of multicultural competence and contribute to the success of intercultural communication in the future, since they allow:

- faster to achieve mutual understanding (41%);
- to form the skills of understanding a communication partner (30%);
- to form the skills of competent verbal / non-verbal communication, thus making intercultural dialogue more successful and effective (29%).

Note that it is precisely multicultural competence that is the main form of communication in the Internet space.

IV. Discussion

For this study, works are of great importance, the objects of which are on the border of the methodology of such sciences as philology, linguistics, cultural studies, sociology. The focus of this work, associated with the peculiarities of intercultural communication in the Internet space as a means of creating multicultural competence, is quite new and relevant [12; 16]. Only a small number of works directly related to the topic of our research exist in Russian science. However, many aspects and principles have been considered in the context of a number of humanitarian disciplines.

Important for our research are the works of Western scientists D. Bell, M. Castells, M. McLuhan, E. Toffler, who consider the characteristic features of the information society, as well as the works of G. S. Batishchev, M. M. Bakhtin, B. Bibler, M. S. Kagan, D. S. Likhachev, Yu. M. Lotman, which set out the problems of dialogue as a driving force of international, intercultural cooperation. The study of the problem of intercultural dialogue as a way of world communication, which includes the interchange of information, thoughts, concepts, cultural assets, is reflected in the works of such scientists as T.G. Grushevitskaya, E.A. Leontovich, T.N. Persikova, A.P. Sadokhin, S.G. Ter-Minasova.

The understanding of intercultural communication through the prism of a philosophical approach, as well as from the point of view of transformations in the social and cultural spheres of society, is found in the works of A.S. Panarin, A.J. Toynbee. Note that scientific research in the field of intercultural communication is diverse: from psychological and sociological to pedagogical and linguistic. It is especially necessary to highlight the works of the French scientist G. Tarde on a retrospective analysis of individual components of intercultural communication, the meaning and likely results of global, all-encompassing communication and its relationship with social aspirations, integration processes and high-intensity development of information technologies [10].

Despite the fact that at present the problems concerning the peculiarities of intercultural communication on the Internet, as well as the influence of the global network on the formation of multicultural competence, are being actively studied, nevertheless, the consideration of the Internet space as a method of intercultural interaction in the student environment was not previously the subject of special scientific research. neither in Russia nor abroad (which, of course, determines the novelty and practical significance of our work).

A problem close to that considered in this work is in the focus of interests of E. Yu. Levina and E. S. Belashova. In the work "Internet space as a means of forming the multicultural

competence of youth", researchers aim to develop organizational and pedagogical forms of using the Internet space as a means of forming multicultural competence among young people [8].

Researchers cite critical and positive factors in the development of the Internet space as a platform for intercultural communication in the context of the educational process of a general educational organization. E. Yu. Levina and E. S. Belashova come to the conclusion that the space of the global network can be regarded as a special, contradictory phenomenon, and its impact on the younger generation is just as contradictory [ibid.]. This requires a large-scale study in terms of creating multicultural competence, using the positive potential of the Internet in the educational process, preventing aggressive content, and likely collisions between personal and social security.

E. A. Korneva in her article "On the issue of intercultural communication on the example of Kazakhstan" touches upon the problem of intercultural communication. The researcher combines it not only with a cognitive interest in other cultures and a tendency to make one's own culture richer, but also with objective social, economic and political processes.

In addition, E. A. Korneva is convinced that an increase in the number of contacts between communicants of different nations and peoples in various spheres of modern social life contributes to the progress and successful development of the process of a global intercultural polylogue [7]. In addition, the scientist emphasizes that the successful experience of Kazakhstan in education and the development of a form of multicultural coexistence causes sincere indifference in the world community, in which the problems of interethnic and interreligious relations have a constant tendency to deteriorate lately.

N.V. Tselepidis in his dissertation "Features of the Internet as a means of intercultural communication among young people" pays special attention to the characteristic features of the content of the Internet space, which make up the information area where representatives of the younger generation spend a lot of time, and also notes such features of the youth environment, as a feeling of compassion, following the models of illusory heroes, the preference for eventfulness, dynamism, activity, the search for entertainment content, transferred from the real life of youth to the virtual Internet space [11].

The scientist justifies the choice of the subject of his research - the disclosure of the main features of the global network space in intercultural communication in the youth environment - by the fact that representatives of the younger generation are more characteristic of spontaneity in creating international and intercultural contacts.

As for the most important results of the study and their scientific novelty, they consist in the fact that for the first time we carried out a study of the features of the Internet space in the intercultural communication of student youth in Russia and Kazakhstan, and identified the main characteristics. On the basis of experiments and comparison of the survey data, the resources that are popular in the Russian and Kazakh students' environment have been analyzed.

V. Conclusion

Intercultural communication is interaction between representatives of different cultures, the essence of which boils down to the interchange of information. In the Internet space, it promotes integration and the formation of multicultural competence, since the Internet creates a unified communication environment and establishes modern rules for the way of life and human communication [14]. In recent years, the Internet space has become an important information and communication source for the majority of Russian and Kazakh students.

The World Wide Web provides a chance for mutual, multicultural communication with almost the entire globe. Online communication with foreign citizens allows you to learn more about the culture of different peoples, their traditions and customs, as well as borrow foreign lexemes and expressions and introduce them into your own language and culture. Undoubtedly, the language barrier may turn out to be an undesirable factor in intercultural communication, but the global network, as an environment for the application of new technologies, to a large extent allows solving problems of this kind.

Internet communication is characterized by the use of both verbal and non-verbal means of communication. The verbal, namely the lexical, aspect of intercultural communication is of particular interest. Taking everything into consideration, having studied the verbal means of Internet communication of students in Russia and Kazakhstan, we can say that from the point of view of vocabulary, the specificity of Internet communication comes down to word formation. In addition, there are cases of occasional use of lexemes. In addition, the lexical aspect of intercultural communication in the Internet space lies in the specifics of computer discourse, which is interpersonal communication in the world wide web. A special place is occupied by onomastic vocabulary, since communicants give themselves names (real or fictitious). The language of Internet communication is dominated by borrowings from English, including English abbreviations.

The impact of the global network on culture is not fully understood at the present time. However, a large number of both positive and negative actions of the World Wide Web have been noticed in relation to the formation of multicultural competence. First of all, this affects the processes of deformation of the language. We think that a painstaking study of the impact of the Internet space on the level of formation of multicultural competence will help the development and improvement of the dialogue and polylogue of cultures in the space of virtual reality.

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